

Nexus between the Brazilian climate commitment on deforestation and agricultural resources: a view of the CLEWs approach

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Context & Challenges

- Context:
 - historically has high rates of deforestation
 - last recent peak: 20 (10³km²) (2022)
 - Most agriculture is rainfed ~ 90%

 - Main challenges:
 - Uncontrolled deforestation threatens the achievement of climate goals and
 - Climate change can have an impact on agricultural production and deforestation increases the risks
- Ensuring agricultural production without compromising forests -> produce and conserve

Research questions and main findings

Research Question(s)

- 1-What are the impacts of controlling deforestation on land use and water use?
- 2-What happens if we consider the impact on productivity resulting from climate change (change in rainfall patterns)?

- The Main Findings:
- Crop production to meet demand for food and bioenergy leads to distinct land use changes with or without deforestation
- Controlling deforestation leads to changes in the area and type of agricultural technologies in relation to water use;

Scenarios

Using the OSeMOSYS Linear Programming Energy System Model the following scenarios were investigated:

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Base line	Reference Permitted Deforestation (no policies) No climate change impacts on agriculture	-Weakness governance -Climate optimism (no impacts of climate change)
Zero_def	-Controlling deforestation -No climate change impacts on agriculture	NDC Commitment – zero deforestation from 2030
Base_imp_CC	Permitted deforestation Climate change impacts in agriculture	Nothing is done. Inaction. Deforestation free and probable climate change impacts on agriculture (less 15% yield all crops)
Zero_def_CC	- Controlling deforestation - Climate change impacts on agriculture	Zero deforestation from 2030 Climate change impacts on agriculture (less 15% yield all crops)

Brazil Reference CLEWs Diagram

Results:

1. Land use change

Delta between scenarios (10^3km^2):⁶

Zero def x base = - 66

Base imp CC x base = -158

Results

Yield

Yield

proj_base

proj_zerodef

Delta (proj_nodef - proj_base)

Results

Technology systems

Area By Crop (Irrigated)

proj_base

zerodef

zerodef_CC

- Maize
- Soybean
- Wheat

Results

Water consumption – agriculture sector

more than doubles!
(51 x 122 m³ billions
of water)

proj_base

proj_ zerodef

zerodef_CC

Conclusions and Policy Insights

-Controlling deforestation requires shifts to more productive technologies, in this case to expand irrigated crops. In turn, they increase water and energy consumption;

-The impacts of climate change, such as reduced rainfall and, consequently, agricultural productivity, lead to greater dependence on irrigated systems;

- considering the scope of the study, the model presented satisfactory results for the intended analysis;

Need to adopt CLEWs analyses in public policies;

Need for technological changes (sustainable transitions) and their frameworks (economic, institutional)

Future Work:

Explore the transition of other land covers (other non-forest vegetation) in the model; explore large-scale restoration scenarios

MANY THANKS

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